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Investigation of the roles of V331 position of NAD⁺ dependent *Ceriporiopsis subvermispota* Formate dehydrogenase and V310 position of NAD⁺ dependent *Chaetomium thermophilum* Formate dehydrogenase enzyme on the reaction mechanism

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Format dehydrogenase (FDH) catalyze the double-sided reaction of CO₂ to formate ion (HCOO⁻), meanwhile it reduces NAD⁺ molecule to NADH. Even though all FDH enzymes have the same function, their kinetic affinity towards the substrates are towards due difference in the structure of their active site pocket. When it is compared to the other well-known NAD⁺ dependent FDH enzymes, *Ceriporiopsis subvermispota* formate dehydrogenase (CsFDH) has lower enzymatic activity in both sides of the reaction¹. Also, it has been observed that *Chaetomium thermophilum* formate dehydrogenase (CtFDH) has highest catalytic activity during formation of HCOO⁻ from CO₂². When these two enzymes have been analysed, it has been seen both of them contains different amino acid sequences on the same position in its catalytic residue. In this study, the roles of V331 position of CsFDH and V310 position of CtFDH in the reaction mechanism have been investigated by using protein engineering. The decided positions have been mutated to threonine amino acid via rational design and changes in the activity of CsFDH of the amino acids in the catalytic domain responsible for the activity of the enzymes. For this purpose, the indicated positions will mutate by the site-directed mutagenesis and these changes will be investigated for the activity of NADH production and importance of the positions for reaction mechanism. The studies will be useful for future studies to understand the role of same position on CtFDH and CsFDH and to regulate the activity of the enzymes.

References:

1. Choe H, Joo JC, Cho DH, Kim MH, Lee SH, et al. (2014) Efficient CO₂-Reducing Activity of NAD-Dependent Formate Dehydrogenase from *Thiobacillus* sp. KNK65MA for Formate Production from CO₂ Gas. PLOS ONE 9. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0103111>
2. Aslan AS, Valjakka J, Ruuponen J, et al. (2017) *Chaetomium thermophilum* formate dehydrogenase has high activity in the reduction of hydrogen carbonate (HCO₃⁻) to formate. PEDS. doi:10.1093/protein/gzw062

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